
OCCASIONAL UPDATE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN PUBLICISTIC TEXT

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Abstract.

The constant interest of linguists in the field of phraseology serves to expand the field of phraseology, to reveal its undiscovered aspects. This article discusses the actualization of phraseological units in French.

Key word.

phraseology, semantic meaning, occasional, unique, actualization of phraseological units.

Introduction

In linguistics, phraseologists usually distinguish between occasional and occasional actualization of phraseological units. Usual actualization does not go beyond the formal and semantic invariance of phraseological units. Unique phraseological units are the basis for the formation of occasional phraseological units, in other words, author phraseological units. In this case, actualization is associated with changes in form and content, which can be expressed in various combinations. Due to the frequent use of phraseological units, they lose their imagery and expressiveness and become speech clichés [Kunin 2005]. A.E. Mamatov distinguishes phraseological units in a broad sense as general changes and individual-author changes.

Material And Methods

A.V. Kunin points to such changes as repetition, replacement of components, long placement (leaving a gap), double actualization, while N.P. Pototskaya distinguishes the types of stylistic updating of phraseological units, including an article or comment, metaphorizing a phraseological unit or its components, replacing one of the lexical components. M.I. Cheremisina talks about four main aspects of variation: definition of words, changing the order of components, morphological or derivative and synonymic, that is, expansion due to replacement with a semantically close word.

Results

Khovanskaya Z.I. and V.G. Kostomarov distinguishes three types of occasional actualization:

- 1) by changing the standard compliance without changing the phraseological units component;
- 2) change/replacement of stable lexical units in phraseological units;
- 3) double actualization of phraseological units.

Discussion

The listed types of occasional actualization have a communicative effect because they include different mechanisms of expressiveness. related to application is metaphorization. Such transformations also affect the sign/denotative side of the meaning of phraseological units.

For example, if we pay attention to the use of the phrase *mince comme une pelure d'oignon* or its synonym *mince comme du papier à cigarette* [PR :Mince, peu épais/thin, thin] in relation to the situation in the newspaper text: *Ce swing State, ou Etat pivot , qui depuis les années 1990 a donné lieu à chaque presidente à des batailles à couteaux tirés, avec un écart thin comme du papier à cigarette, est en train de devenir un laboratory ultraconservateur inspirée de la Hungary illibérale de Viktor Orbán.* (from the 1990s This swing state or core state, which has fueled every presidential contest by a (cigarette-paper-thin) margin, is becoming an ultra-conservative testing ground inspired by Viktor Orbán's illiberal Hungary.) [L'OBS/N°3041- 19/01/2023, p-38] in the sentence *un écart* [PR :Distance qui sépare deux choses qu'on écarte ou qui s'écartent.]-space lexical unit is not suitable for the comparison feature as thin as a cigarette paper, but the author is used to indicate how tense the situation is.

The communicative effect is achieved through an additional expressive tool, metaphorical ellipsis of the literal and figurative meanings of the phrase, the occasional use of phraseological units revives in memory the variable phrase that is the basis for the comparative phraseological units, Updates: the situation is as thin and thin as the paper of a cigarette. clearly shows the image/situation.

At the end of the review of writer and film critic Hélène Frappat's work entitled "Trois femmes disparaissent", journalist Élisabeth Philippe commented on the writer's work: *De son écriture raffinée comme des ongles peints, elle griffe les images dont les femmes sont captives et ménage une brèche, une échappée belle.* [L'OBS/N°3039-05/01/2023,p-71], he points to the sharp pen of the writer.

At the same time, the change of the content plan associated with the violation of the formal stability of the comparative phraseological units at the lexical level is determined by the introduction of additional symbols that adapt the comparative phraseological unit to the context, replacing it with a synonym, paronym or homonym. A stable comparison of additional signs and a connection for compression - the introduction of additional actualizers into the internal context of phraseological units, expands the structure of phraseological units, its structural composition, and adds additional meanings specific to the situation.

For example, from the Politics column: En Vendée, Bruno Retailleau se sent comme un poisson dans l'eau. "Il est apprécié pour sa constance et la sincérité de ses convictions." Même ceux qui ne partagent pas ses opinions reconnaissent son travail », assure la sénatrice Billon. Even those who disagree with him recognize his work," says Senator Billon.)[LE FIGARO mercredi 16 septembre 2020, p-7,]

From the column INTERNATIONAL : Nétanyahou signe une entente historique avec des pays du Golfe à la Maison-Blanche. Pour Trump, cet accord avec les Émirats et Bahreïn marque l'avènement d'un "nouveau Moyen-Orient". Considered by the Palestinian Authority as "coups de poignard dans le dos", ces accords entérinent l'idée qu'il est possible pour une nation arabe de s'afficher espace aérien saoudien. ()[LE FIGARO mercredi 16 septembre 2020, p-10,]

Journalist Arnaud Leparmentier from the Économie & entreprise rubric: Très sérieusement, celui qui a bâti le dernier quartier ultraluxe de la ville assure : « [A New York], nous avons construit à l'excès comme des fous et nous avons eu un mauvais leadership ", explique M. Ross, qui ajoute : « Nous arrivions au point où personne ne pouvait réellement se permettre de vivre ici. (The man who built the city's last super-luxury district earnestly assures us: "[In New York] we built like crazy and we had bad leadership," Mr. Ross explains, adding: " This is the point where no one can live.") [MERCREDI 16 SEPTEMBER 2020, Le Monde, p-18]

Dossier spécial : V É H I C U L E S É L E C T R I Q U E S rubric: Au feu rouge, la SR/S (motorcycle model) n'en suscite pas moins une curiosité teintée d'empathie. Voire d'une forme de respect, eu égard à sa façon de jaillir comme un diable de sa boîte. "change is a state to be appreciated." [WEDNESDAY 16 SEPTEMBER 2020, Le Monde, p-22]

From the Culture column: from an interview with Belgian actress Emilie Dequenne: En 2012, elle a vu apparaître les premières taches sur les doigts. Cinq ans plus tard, elle est « blanche comme neige ». C'est bien, "je prends la lumière", dit-elle, préférant en rire. (In 2012, he saw the first spots appear on his fingers. Five years

later he will grow old as white as snow.-. Okay, "I'll take the lamp", he says, preferring to laugh.)[MERCREDI 16 SEPTEMBER 2020, Le Monde, p-27]

In the review of the film "Antoinette dans les Cévennes" by Clarisse Fabre, a journalist from the Culture section explains that the action of the hero of the film to rein in the donkey is inescapable with chercher comme une aiguille dans une botte de foin (literally: looking for a needle in a haystack). and this laborious effort Démarrant son périple avec Patrick, cherchant Vladimir comme une aiguille dans une botte de foin, Antoinette met ses nerfs à rude épreuve et se trouve démunie face à cet animal qui lui résiste. C'est une mine de gags, à jet continu, jusqu'à ce qu'Antoinette approvoise l'âne. tests and is powerless in front of this animal that resists her. Antoinette is in a constant mine of gags (blague, comic situations) until she manages to rein in the donkey.[MERCREDI 16 SEPTEMBER 2020, Le Monde, p-26]

Fabrice Nicolino and Riess use the idiom brûler comme au fer rouge to describe the extreme suffering from the horrific incident in an article covering the trial of the racist crime of Charlie Hebdo: Il souffrait horriblement d'être accusé de racisme. C'était comme le brûler au fer rouge. "(He suffered terribly from being accused of racism. It was like being burned with a hot iron).[VENDREDI 11 SEPTEMBER 2020, p-8]

In the Disparitions column, an article about the crimes of a Cambodian prison warden nicknamed Duch, he recruits teenagers as guards during his service, because teenagers are blank and clean like white paper, and it is easy to subjugate them. writes about what he considers to be a lady : Douch est d'abord nommé vice président chargé du groupe d'interrogateurs, puis, en mars 1976, devient le seul responsable du camp. Il s'entoure de ses anciens subordonnés de M13, en qui il a toute confiance, et recrute comme gardiens des adolescents, car ils sont, selon lui, « comme une feuille blanche »(fam.), facilement indoctrinables.[JEUDI 3 SEPTEMBER 2020, p-21]

From the TECH column: La situation est plus compliquée pour Ericsson et Nokia : dans la plupart des pays européens, ils sont encore concon à la concurrence chinoise alors que leur commercial presence en Chine se réduit comme peau de grin. De plus, ils n'ont pas les mêmes moyens que leurs rivaux chinois pour financer leur R&D. For Ericsson and Nokia, the situation is more complicated: in most European countries, they face Chinese competition at a time when their commercial presence in China is shrinking. do not have the same opportunities to finance R&D as their Chinese rivals.)mercredi 2 septembre 2020 LE FIGARO, p-22)

From the INTERNATIONAL rubric: En attendant, l'épidémie a laissé des traces sur le tissu économique et social, notably dans la capitale surveillée comme le milk sur le feu par le pouvoir. Malgré le retour des embouteillages, « il y a moins de monde qu'avant. J'ai l'impression que beaucoup de gens ont quitté Pékin et ne reviendront plus », confie Chen Yu. has left its mark on the capital, which is being closely watched by the authorities. Despite the return of traffic jams, "there are fewer people than before. I got the impression that a lot of people have left Beijing and are not coming back," says Chen Yu.) [jeudi 3 septembre 2020 LE FIGARO, p-8]

L'économie : « Il faut boire de la vodka en deux occasions seulement. Quand on mange, et quand on ne mange pas. » Malgré cet imparable proverbe russe, Absolut procure comme une gueule de bois [désagréables symptômes d'un lendemain de cuite ; grande fatigue après une soirée trop festive ; veisalgia; xylostome; casque à bolons ; mauvais goût dans la bouche après avoir trop bu, dû à un abuse d'alcool] différée à Pernod Ricard, vu la dépréciation pour cause de coronavirus de la marque suédoise, plus de dix ans après son rachat. (" You should only drink vodka twice. When you eat and when you don't eat" Despite this popular Russian saying, the Swedish for Pernod Ricard taking into account the devaluation of the brand due to the coronavirus, there is no growth after more than a decade.)[Jeudi 3 septembre 2020 Les Echos, p-32].

CONCLUSION

In the process of studying the use of comparative phraseological units in newspaper texts, many examples of replacement of comparison components were found, which in this work are called component rearrangement. Its essence is as follows: the author of the article uses several comparative phraseological units in a row in one context, but switches their amplifiers. Thus, a contradictory effect appears: the standards are not in any way for these characteristics. The modified comparative phraseological units takes on the exact opposite meaning, and due to the unusual, unpredictable nature of such a replacement, the expressiveness of the modified phraseological units increases.

As a result of the analysis of cases of occasional use of comparative phraseological units, it can be concluded that comparative phraseological units can be widely modified in various ways. Occasionality is an effective way to increase the expressiveness of original phraseological units. Such changes can only lead to changes in the connotative and denotative structure of the usual comparative phraseological units. Occasional changes in both macrocomponents of the

semantics of phraseological units have the highest communicative effect. It is difficult to give a precise quantitative description of the increase of communicative influence, because, as a rule, changes affect one microcomponent of connotation and create several meaningful situations at the same time. Communicative effect directly depends on two conditions: unusualness, unpredictability of occasional changes and how well they correspond to the communicative situation of the newspaper text.

Semantic change of comparative phraseological units is carried out in the process of their interaction with the contextual environment. Along with double actualization, it leads to the activation of direct meaning and the formation of a new meaning in case of violation of the semantic valence of the comparative phraseological unit.

Acknowledgement

The text of the newspaper and journalistic speech illuminates the social system of important socio-political events and is intended for a wide audience. Various materials in the text of the newspaper are combined with a common goal, the main functions of the text are to convey information and influence. The press not only covers the events, but also sets the goal of influencing the addressee, who is generalized within a certain ideology. The ability of the newspaper text to influence the addressee is the result of the choice of the addressee's message content and the way of its linguistic expression.

Phraseological units, in particular, comparative phraseological units, play an important role since the language of print media is defined as a combination of standard and expressive language tools that can convey not only information, but also attitudes to what is reported. Comparative phraseological units are both standard and expressive language tools of the newspaper text. Marking of comparative phraseological units to the standard language tools of the newspaper text is based on the possibility of using them as templates and stamps. The expressiveness of comparative phraseological units occurs when the components of the connotative meaning are updated in the newspaper text.

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